

COMPUTER-ASSISTED LANGUAGE LEARNING IN FROG VLE PROMOTES ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING AMONG STUDENT

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ABSTRACT

In 21st-century learning, it is essential for English teachers to integrate technology into teaching and learning processes in the classroom. FROG Virtual Learning Environment (FROG VLE) has become the latest method introduced by the Ministry of Education in order to achieve the objective of Malaysia Education Blueprint 2018 – 2025 where students acquire English as the target language via a virtual learning environment. FROG VLE is a cloud-based learning environment that emulates the traditional face-to-face teaching and learning processes in the classroom. It is the government's initiative to leverage technology usage in secondary schools all over Malaysia. In this qualitative study carried out in Sekolah Menengah Kebangsaan (P) Sultan Ibrahim, eight form five students were chosen using purposive sampling. In order to ensure that the data are valid and reliable, three research instruments were used which were observation, semi-structured interview, and focus group. The Nvivo software was used by the researcher to analyze all the data qualitatively according to specific themes which were students' self-esteem, students' anxiety, students' motivation, the impact of FROG VLE, school facilities, academic achievement, and students' readiness in using technology. The findings of this study showed that FROG VLE was an interactive learning tool that attracted students' interest in learning the English language. Students had the opportunity to discuss their work with their group members and submit their group tasks online. FROG Play was the latest application that had been introduced to the students in FROG VLE in which students had the chance to play any educational games related to their English lessons that had been uploaded by their English teacher. It also revealed that FROG VLE was able to increase students' self-esteem, manage to reduce students' anxiety and at the same time, motivate students in learning English language. The students' were able to apply collaborative learning with FROG VLE by using the online learning platform (Canva, Padlet, Wordwall) and software applications (Microsoft Office, video recording) for their online presentation.

Keywords: Computer, technology, Frog VLE, English language, virtual learning

INTRODUCTION

Technology has become the latest approach that teachers need to integrate into 21st-century classrooms. Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) can be defined as a set of instructions that need to be loaded on the computer in order to be able to work in the language room, Stockwell (2013). This helps teachers prepare teaching materials that include four English language skills in the classroom. Students who are actively involved during the learning activities will perform better, especially in examinations. Today, students prefer to use computers in the classroom because they can find lots of information related to the topics by the teacher. Learning has become more enjoyable when teachers play the role of supervisor for students to complete their assignments. This will make the students learn independently.

FROG Virtual Learning Environment (FROG VLE) had been introduced in 2013 to all Malaysian government schools as a new medium of instruction that teachers must use for teaching and learning purposes. FROG VLE is a teaching method based on Malaysia's expanding internet technology which involves 1 Bestari Net Project that collaborates with YTL Communication Company and FROG Asia. Under 1 Bestari Net, schools will be equipped with an integrated solution allowing teaching, learning, collaboration, and administrative functions to take place through the Internet-based FROG VLE which can be accessed in and out of the schools. By using FROG VLE English teachers can create interesting sites with short notes, videos, and PowerPoint slides where students can access the information and learn independently. It is worth noting that parents can also observe their children's activities in FROG VLE using their own accounts which will be linked to their children's and teachers' accounts. Parents can communicate with teachers online and observe their children's learning progress anytime.

RESEARCH PROBLEM

Most of the Malaysian students lack self-esteem in speaking English because they prefer to use their mother tongue (Malay) for communication. This happens because the Malay language is the National language of Malaysia whereas the English language is the second language for people to master. Idrus and Salleh (2017) mentioned that students from University Technology PETRONAS have low self-esteem in speaking English. They are not confident in speaking English in their daily lives although their lecturers use English for teaching purposes. They have difficulty understanding the English language because they cannot comprehend the instructions given by English teachers in the classroom. Most of them feel anxious about speaking English due to a lack of exposure to the English language. Lacking self-confidence in speaking English increases the level of anxiety in learning the English language, especially in the classroom setting. Akkakoson (2016) has conducted a case study among King Mongkut University students in Thailand focusing on the conceptualization of English language speaking in classrooms. The focus of this study was on students' anxiety and attitudes toward the use of the English language during class. He concluded that students with low anxiety speak the English language fluently as compared to students with a higher level of anxiety.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. How does the use of FROG VLE increase self-esteem among students in learning the English language?
2. How does FROG VLE decrease students' anxiety in learning the English language?
3. How does FROG VLE motivate students in learning the English language?

4. What are the impacts of using FROG VLE among students in learning the English language?

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To investigate how FROG VLE can be used to increase self-esteem among students in learning the English language.
2. To determine if FROG VLE decreases students' anxiety in learning the English language.
3. To explore students' motivation in using FROG VLE in learning the English language.
4. To determine the impact of using FROG VLE among students in learning the English language.

SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

The findings of this study help teachers to utilize FROG VLE to transfer knowledge among secondary school students. 21st-century learning concepts should be more towards a student-centred approach and technology should be the medium that teachers use to maximize the level of students' understanding of specific topics for every lesson. The information from this qualitative research will help teachers either in public or private schools to identify suitable pedagogical approaches to teaching the English language in the classroom. Every teacher has their own way and method of conducting the lessons, but they need to consider students' interests so that students will pay full attention during teaching and learning, especially in the classroom.

LITERATURE REVIEW

MASLOW'S HIERARCHY OF NEEDS

This theory is very popular, and it is widely being used in the educational area since a long time ago. In this theory, Maslow suggested that before individuals meet their full potential, they need to accomplish every level of needs based on Maslow's Hierarchy pyramid. Maslow's theory can be considered the father of humanistic psychology, and he was born in 1908. He was well-known for his hierarchy of human needs which he called a theory of motivation. He believes that every person was born with a set of basic needs: 1) physiological, 2) safety needs, 3) belongingness or love, 4) self-esteem and 5) self-actualization. Knud (2018) had done much quantitative research in different universities and reported similar findings where university students show positive improvement when their lecturers integrate technology during the lecture. The online learning space embarks on lighter examination, intricate discussion, and ease of communication especially the career pathways among learners.

INTEGRATING FROG VLE

Cheok, Wong, Ayub, Mahmud (2017) and Rajani (2018) define that FROG VLE is an intranet, online classroom, and social space for the school. It is a web-based learning system that replicates real-world learning by integrating virtual equivalents of conventional concepts of education. For

example, teachers can assign lessons, tests, and marks virtually while students can submit homework and view their marks through the FROG VLE. Parents can communicate with schools while school administrators can organize their school calendars and disseminate school notices via the Internet. Moreover, FROG VLE can be accessed anywhere as long as students have Internet connection. The FROG VLE has been created with the user inside the website. It is aimed at nurturing a creating generation of Malaysians who are empowered to take ownership of their education and are prepared to compete in a global knowledge-based economy.

COMPUTER ASSISTED LANGUAGE LEARNING IN MALAYSIA EDUCATION

According to Wu, Wen, Marek, Michael (2010); Wu, Fitzgerald, Yu, & Witten, (2019) CALL can be defined as the study of applications via computer in language teaching and learning process. Their research come out with a solid foundation whereas CALL become an effective instructional tool for educators during their teaching process in the classroom. Computers can do some of the work of the teacher and provide great assistance for the students. Students can easily access any information that they want and look back at the online notes that have been uploaded by their teachers in FROG VLE. A study by Harun et al. (2016) in Islamic schools showed that Islamic education teachers in the Muar district have a high level of skills in using FROG VLE applications and they prefer to apply this technology tool to increase their students' interest and motivation in learning the Islamic education subject. The Pond feature in FROG VLE was the medium for students to discuss their presentation online which enables them to be more prepared for group work and obtain high marks. Most of the teachers prepare interactive quizzes and they allow students to revise their lessons by accessing the specific website at home.

VIRTUAL LEARNING CLASSROOM IN MALAYSIA

Collaborative learning in social blended E-Learning especially FROG VLE has been applied a long time ago in Malaysia's Education System as a good step to introduce technology during the teaching and learning process in the classroom. This application provides more opportunities for students to exchange their ideas during online discussions. They can watch videos that have been uploaded by their English teachers and come out with their own conclusion. English teachers may use their creativity to hyperlink special educational websites to this FROG VLE application. Harun et al. (2016) have conducted quantitative research to identify the level of readiness of the Islamic education teachers in the district of Muar using FROG VLE as a tool of teaching and learning in the schools. In the Malaysia Education system, FROG VLE is the latest software that English teachers should use for their teaching purposes. By integrating technology in classrooms, English teachers can ease their burdens because online assignment submissions are marked through the online system automatically. They just need to equip themselves with technological knowledge because technology is a helpful gadget that can be used by everyone. In 21st-century learning, English teachers must equip themselves with ICT knowledge so that they can plan for an interesting and enjoyable lesson in the classroom. By using FROG VLE, students will not feel bored anymore and they can participate actively during the English lesson.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher conducted qualitative research to explore how CALL through FROG VLE can promote English language learning among form five students from Sekolah Menengah Kebangsaan (P) Sultan Ibrahim which is located in Larkin, Johor Bahru. Eight female students had been chosen via using purposive sampling to obtain data. Three research instruments; semi-structured interview, observation and focus group were used to collect the data. This is the triangulation method where at least three types of research instruments must be selected in conducting qualitative research to make sure the data that the researcher obtained are valid and reliable.

RESULTS

Question	Participant's Response
How does the use of FROG VLE increase self-esteem among students in learning the English language?	<p>Student 1 <i>"... by using technology it makes me become more confidence in delivering my points because I can search for more information more precisely before the presentation. When I am well prepared, I will not feel scare if my friends ask me any questions and it actually increase my self-esteem. I think my friends also undergo the same situation in their own lives..."</i></p> <p>Student 3 <i>"As for me, I like to use technology such as Microsoft Power Point and download related video for my topic so that I can amuse my friends. It makes my presentation becomes unique and I think I will get extra mark from my English teacher. If I do not use technology and need to speak English by myself, it increase my level of anxiety and I end up speaking out of the topic"</i></p> <p>Student 4 <i>"when English teacher uses technology during the English lesson, it means that she wants her students to access for more information about the topic by themselves. Students will be actively search for more information and when teacher asks question, they can answer it very well. From here the impact of FROG VLE can increase the self-esteem among students in learning English language. It is a good thing and I like so much if I can participate actively and contribute something during the English lesson in the classroom"</i></p>
How does FROG VLE decrease students' anxiety in learning the English language?	<p>Student 1 <i>"... by using technology it makes me less nervous because my friends do not pay hundred percent attention towards me. They are watching the slides that I have prepared earlier. I can explain more bravely because at least there are some points that I can refer if I am getting nervous. For me, point that I put in my slides during the presentation time is a good back up for someone that are having stage fright like me.."</i></p> <p>Student 2 <i>"I will become less anxiety when I am using technology because it make me become more comfortable in delivering my speech."</i></p>

	<i>Technology actually help me to overcome my frighteners in speaking in front of my friends. For example, when I am completing my assignment to interview one of the successful businessman, I can retake my video. I feel more convenience in speaking in front of the camera although I know that I need to upload the video through FROG VLE."</i>
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How does FROG VLE motivate students in learning the English language?	<p>Student 1 <i>"Although my parents do not speak English but I do not think it is a big hurdle for me to master English language because they always motivate me to read English newspaper such as New Strait Time and The Star during the weekend. My dad will be buying me the newspaper and asks me to read all of the news in order to increase my knowledge with what happen all around the world and at the same I can improve my English skills so that I will be more comfortable in using English"</i></p> <p>Student 2 <i>"As for me, by watching the English video it motivates me to speak just like the native speaker. I can improve my speaking skill by correcting my intonation, accent and pronunciation just like the real English speaker. Besides that, video helps me digest the information easily without need to read the literature textbook. For example, last month my English teacher shows some video about Sonnet 18. It is a famous poem and it maybe come out during SPM later on and I cannot understand it due to language barrier. However, after my English teacher shows a short video about the poem, I am finally understanding it clearly and manage to remember all of the important components such as literal meaning, themes, figurative meanings, persona and moral values. Before exam, I just need to log in to my FROG VLE account and refer to all notes and videos that my English teacher has upload."</i></p> <p>Student 4 <i>" I am personally feel motivate in learning English language because by simplifying the using of technology it make me become external motivate to complete my work. I will be completing my work before the due date because there is Notification feature inside the FROG VLE where I will be reminding of my assignment whenever I log in into my FROG VLE account. Besides that, I can see my performance at the "Analyse" feature inside the FROG VLE. If my English teacher satisfy with my achievement, I will be given rewards"</i></p>
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What are the impacts of using FROG VLE among students in learning the English language?	<p>Student 1 <i>"I think FROG VLE is a good software because it is actually similar with the blog system where the user can upload anything so that the readers can enjoy reading new information. The differences between these two applications is FROG VLE is more toward education purpose while blog we can post anything"</i></p> <p>Student 2 <i>"I like FROG VLE software because I can send my homework through online by using the File Drop feature. It is a place where students can</i></p>
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	<p><i>upload and download their assignments easily. I just need to go to my class file which is 5 Elite. Together with assignment, my English teacher will put the due date so that my friends and I will be aware with our due date and become more responsible. If I have any difficulty to finish my assignment, I can discuss it with my friends through forum features. If my English teacher is free, she will help us and join the forum. For me technology can become the platform for me to do my assignment through online. We do not need to be physically together anymore"</i></p> <p>Student 5 <i>"It is an interactive software because FROG VLE not only can be access by laptop or Chromebook but by my smartphones too. Right now, we can learn through online by using modern gadget. It makes learning process become more enjoyable. FROG VLE is an interesting application that change the meaning of learning compare than before. As young generation, I like to use modern gadgets for learning purpose compare to traditional way"</i></p> <p>Student 7 <i>"I think FROG VLE is an interactive software because they are many interesting and fun features inside it. For example, the FROG Play application. It is a gaming platform where I am able to progress my study through challenging quizzes while unlocking fun mini- games. By doing that, I can revise my English lesson at my own pace. As for me, the more I play, the more I learn. It is a new thing that I can do where I did not feel bored anymore especially when I am revising my English lesson through FROG VLE"</i></p>
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CONCLUSION

In Malaysia, English teachers use FROG VLE to attract students' interest in learning the English language subject and the learning process becomes more interactive when students are able to submit their homework online. In the virtual learning environment, English teachers can save valuable time grading students' assignments as the assignments are automatically assessed after setting up the allocated marks in the FROG VLE. If students submit their assignments before the due date and they have done impressive work, English teachers can reward their students with extra points. By using the points, students can do many things such as upgrading their avatar, playing educational games, or buying online interactive books so that their learning process becomes more fun and enjoyable. FROG VLE has become the main mechanism for supporting online education in secondary schools in Malaysia. The Ministry of Education wants all English teachers to integrate technology, especially FROG VLE because the young generation nowadays uses technology as part of their learning process not only at school but also at home. Most of the students have smartphones and they can use it to access their FROG VLE account. Instead of letting this Net generation waste their time on social networking sites such as Facebook and Instagram, it is better for them to do their revision through FROG VLE. There are many interesting notes and educational videos which were uploaded by their English teachers that will benefit students in their learning as long as they have access to their FROG VLE accounts.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this manuscript.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

All authors are participants in the data collection, analysis, writing and revising the manuscript.

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